

Dyer, N.A., Lucas, E.R., Nagi, S.C., McDermott, D.P., Brenas, J.H., Miles, A., Clarkson, C.S., Mawejje, H.D., Wilding, C.S., Halfon, M.S., Asma, H., Heinz, E., Donnelly, M.J., Mechanisms of transcriptional regulation in *Anopheles gambiae* revealed by allele specific expression
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Supplementary figures and Methods

Supplementary figure 1

- a. PCA of gene expression for reciprocal crosses. Mapping of RNAseq sample names to crosses: Wilding_1: B1, Wilding_2: B3, Wilding_3: B5, Wilding_4: K2, Wilding_5: K4, Wilding_6: K6
- b. PCA of gene expression for crosses compared to other *Anopheles gambiae* sl strains: Teifora_9, Teifora_8 and Teifora_13 are Teifora colony pools, Kis1, Kis2, Kis3 and Kis4 are Kisumu colony pools, BusRes1, BusRes2, BusRes3, BusRes4, BusRes5, BusRes6 are Busia G28 deltamethrin selected colony pools, and Wilding_1, Wilding_2, Wilding_3, Wilding_4, Wilding_5 and Wilding_6 are the same as in panel a.

Supplementary Figure 2

Plots of total read count against ASE at each SNP. Note that SNPs with 100 or more reads are additionally shown in Figure 3 in the main article. The red dotted line indicates the cut off of SNPs with at least ten reads used to calculate gene level ASE. Cross and source of SNPs used to count reads are indicated at the top of each plot. For crosses B5, K2 and K6 the SNP ASE indicates maternal reads/total reads at SNP and for crosses B1 and B3 SNP ASE indicates reference reads/total reads at SNP. Cross K6 is shown with ASE inferred using SNPs from both the parents of cross K4 and for the initially assumed parents of cross K6.

Supplementary Figure 3

Allele balance calculated using SNPs from non-parents

Plots of total read count against ASE at each SNP.

- a. RNAseq reads from progeny of cross K2 mapped to K4 parents
- b. RNAseq reads from progeny of cross K2 mapped to mother of cross K6 and correct father
- c. RNAseq reads from progeny of cross K2 mapped to mother of cross K4 and correct father

- d. RNAseq reads from progeny of cross K4 mapped to mother of cross K6 and correct father

Supplementary Figure 4

Progeny of crosses K4 (Wilding 5) and K6 (Wilding 6) are genetically similar

PCA-3L-WildingAllelicImbalance

PCA-3R-WildingAllelicImbalance

PCA-X-WildingAllelicImbalance

PCA of sequences inferred by calling SNPs from RNAseq data of crosses between Kisumu and Nagongera colonies. Left plots are, PC1 vs PC2, right plots are PC2 vs PC3. The chromosomal arm for each pair of plots is indicated in the plot titles. % of variance explained by each component is given in brackets in the axis labels.

Supplementary figure 5

Chromosomal distribution of genes showing ASE

a.

b.

C.

d.

e.

f.

g.

h.

- a. Bar plot of the proportion of genes showing allele specific expression/ total genes containing suitable SNPs to detect ASE per chromosome arm. Colours indicate the different crosses. X chromosomal SNPs were not available for crosses B1 and B3.
- b. Proportion of genes showing allelic imbalance compared to all genes where SNPs were present so ASE could have been detected along each chromosomal arm. Error bars show standard deviation across the 6 crosses.
- c. -h. plots of major allele frequency (MAF) along each chromosomal arm. Scatter plot above each chromosomal arm of genes for which the P value for ASE was non-significant (blue), and genes where the P value for ASE was significant at $\alpha = 0.05$ following FDR correction (orange). The density of data along the chromosomal arms is on a black to blue to white scale: black regions indicate no data.
- c. Genes showing ASE and not showing ASE along each chromosome arm for cross B1)
- d. Genes showing ASE and not showing ASE along each chromosome arm for cross B3
- e. Genes showing ASE and not showing ASE along each chromosome arm for cross B5
- f. Genes showing ASE and not showing ASE along each chromosome arm for cross K2
- g. Genes showing ASE and not showing ASE along each chromosome arm for cross K4
- h. Genes showing ASE and not showing ASE along each chromosome arm for cross K6

Supplementary Methods

Determining cross fathers using Mendelian error

For the autosomes for each cross where the mother's genome sequence was of sufficient quality (K2, K4, K6 and B5), the per progeny sample Mendelian error was calculated for each possible parental pair of the known mother with all potential fathers using scikit-allel version 1.3.7 (1). The father in the parental pair that had the smallest median progeny sample Mendelian error on at least 3 autosomal arms was deemed to be the true father. Supplementary table 1 shows the median progeny sample Mendelian error for all potential fathers on each autosomal arm.

Genome analysis

Scikit-allel version 1.3.7 (1) was used to calculate the nucleotide diversity and the percentage of heterozygous sites for the parental colonies and 112 previously described wild *Anopheles gambiae* collected from Nagongera in 2012 (2)

The sequenced genomes of all mothers and potential fathers were screened for target site mutation L995S in the voltage gated sodium channel (AGAP004707) and G280S in *ace1* (AGAP001356). For Nagongera colony individuals, 2/16 were homozygous and 10/16 were heterozygous for the voltage gated sodium channel L995S mutation, and 9/14 were heterozygous for the *ace1* G280S mutation. This is consistent with Isaacs *et al* 2018 observation of one of 40 Nagongera females being a 280G/280S heterozygote (3). 1/16 Kisumu colony individuals were also heterozygous for each of these mutations.

CNV analysis

We used the CNV calls for Ag1000g phase 3, which applied a Gaussian hidden Markov Model (HMM) to the normalized windowed coverage data for each genotyped individual as

described in Lucas et al 2019 (4). CNV was deemed possible if any of the parents and F1 siblings from crosses B5, K2, K4 or K6 (total 63 individuals) had a copy number call other than 2 on the autosomes. As ASE could not be inferred on the X chromosome for crosses B1 and B3 we excluded it from the analysis. The father of cross B5, AC0416-C had high variance in copy number calls and was therefore removed from CNV analysis.

Selective Sweeps

To assess selective sweeps, lists of genes either showing ASE or having SNPs to detect ASE but not showing ASE were compared to a database of regions under selection in the *Anopheles* selection atlas (5) as defined by H_{12} signal (6) both across the range of *Anopheles gambiae* and restricted to Uganda using a custom Python script (https://github.com/azurillandfriend/sweeps_ASE.git).

Enrichment analysis

Hypergeometric tests for enrichment of gene ontology terms, Pfam protein domain enrichment, and KEGG pathways were implemented using python (7). The test set for each cross was the set of genes showing significant ASE following FDR correction, and the “universe set” was the set of genes for each cross that had at least 10 reads containing SNPs distinguishing maternal and paternal alleles.

Gene age analysis

The evolutionary age of genes was taken from the Princeton Protein Orthology Database PPODv4_PTHR7-OrthoMCL (8), with age estimates based on Wagner parsimony. A gene age enrichment test was implemented using the `age_enrichment.py` script in ProteinHistorian (9), using option ‘-a ignore’ to ignore the proteins not present in the database. P values were obtained using a Mann Whitney U test for difference in overall age distribution between sets and Fisher’s exact test for difference in fraction of proteins in each age in the set. The null

hypothesis that the proportion of ASE genes does not differ between autosome arms, was tested using a two-sided Fisher's exact test (where the counts were too high for efficient computation P value was simulated using 2000 replicates).

Selection of SNPs to detect ASE

Detection of ASE relies on sufficient SNP differing between the parents (10). The number of SNPs differing between maternal and paternal genomes varied (Table 2). For crosses B1 and B3, with parent genomes unavailable, we instead attempted to use parental colony consensus genome sequences for mapping. However, the number of SNPs differing in Nagongera and Kisumu consensus sequences (Table 3) was insufficient for ASE analysis. The low number of differing SNPs may be due to barriers to recombination imposed by the genome structure of *Anopheles gambiae*, which limit the extent to which colonies become inbred, with heterozygosity persisting even after many generations of inbreeding (11). This contrasts with *Drosophila* where colony genotypes have been used effectively for inference of ASE (12, 13). Since the mosquitoes were pooled prior to RNA extraction, inferring SNPs from the RNAseq data to detect ASE is problematic, since most SNPs are heterozygous in one or both parents, resulting in a mixture of homozygous and heterozygous SNPs in the progeny, and we would not know at each SNP whether to test for deviation from 1:1 expression or 3:1 expression. To increase the number of SNPs to detect ASE in these pooled samples we therefore used the siblings of the RNA sequenced F1 to infer which SNPs were homozygous but different between the parents (opposite homozygous SNPs). Such SNPs were selected using the following criteria: SNPs must be heterozygous and biallelic in all siblings where data was available. We excluded SNPs for which five or more siblings had missing data (code available

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10479484). Since F1 genome data was unphased, it was not possible to assign SNPs to either the Kisumu or Nagongera parent.

For a Mendelian inherited SNP, opposite homozygous SNP in parents should result in all progeny having heterozygous biallelic SNP. If one or both parents were heterozygous (biallelic) then 50% of the progeny are expected to be heterozygous, and the probability of all the progeny being heterozygous in this situation is given by the binomial probability density function where $p=0.5$, the number of trials (per SNP) is the number of progeny and the number of “successes” is also the number of progeny. The number of progeny and SNPs per chromosome arm where all progeny were heterozygous is given in supplementary table 2. Almost all sequenced siblings were male, the heterogametic sex in *An. gambiae*, so it was not possible to infer SNPs on the X chromosome using this method.

The suitability of these SNPs to detect ASE was first tested by comparing the SNPs inferred from the siblings to those inferred from the parents, where parental genotypes were known (supplementary table 3). Most SNPs were shared between the parents and siblings, with only a small fraction (<7.5%) unique to the siblings. The total number of usable SNPs from the siblings was lower than those in the parents: a reduction of between 6% and 16%. Per SNP ASE was calculated as counts at reference SNP/counts at reference SNP plus counts at alternative SNP for the sibling SNPs, and as counts at maternal SNP/ counts at maternal plus paternal SNP for parent SNPs. The mean per SNP ASE for SNPs with at least 10 reads counted remained between 0.49 and 0.51 confirming that the SNPs are likely to be heterozygous in the F1 and that mapping bias is not a problem for this dataset. The standard deviation of per SNP ASE increased very slightly (from 0.12-0.14 to 0.13 to 0.15). For crosses B1 and B3, the per SNP ASE was in line with the other crosses with mean 0.5 and standard deviation 0.13 and 0.15 respectively. However, when the per SNP ASE was plotted against the total counts at

each SNP, a cluster of SNPs with high ASE and expression was seen for the sibling but not parent inferred SNPs (Figure 3, supplementary figure 2).

The properties of SNPs inferred from parents and siblings were additionally compared by inferring parental pseudogenomes and running ASEReadCounter* with both sets of SNPs. SNPs in crosses K2, K4 and B5 that were unique to siblings and with high ASE ($< .25$ or $> .75$) and high expression (>100 counts) were therefore removed from the analysis for crosses B1 and B3 before inferring per gene ASE.

Calculation of overdispersion parameter

Due to overdispersion, RNAseq data is not binomially distributed but can be better described by a beta binomial distribution. The distribution of counts data and overdispersion parameter ρ for the beta binomial distribution was calculated using the counts data for each cross, including the counts for the SNP with the maximum counts in each gene (with minimum 10 counts), using the R package glmmTMB (14), which uses maximum likelihood estimation to fit binomial and beta binomial model to the read count data for each cross. Models were compared using ANOVA in base R (15). ANOVA indicated that the beta binomial model was a better fit to the data than the binomial ($P < 2.2e-16$). The dispersion parameter $\phi(\text{disp})$ for the beta binomial distribution of counts data for crosses B1, B3, B5, K2, and K4 was estimated at 25.8, giving a $\rho = 1/(1+\phi(\text{disp}))$ of 0.038.

The properties of SNPs inferred from parents and siblings were compared by inferring parental pseudogenomes and running ASEReadCounter* with both sets of SNPs.

Allelic analysis of ASE

For SNPs inferred from parents, allelic count tables were additionally analyzed using Qllelic (16) with a binomial test of the null hypothesis of equal numbers of transcripts arising from maternal and paternal alleles. ASE was considered significant at $p=0.05$ following Bonferroni

correction. As technical replicates were unavailable, an exploratory solution for correcting overdispersion was splitting reads into groups. This produced a consistent quality correction constant (QCC) value of 1.56 for QCC correction. R packages UpSetR (17), stats (15) and ggplot2 (18) were used for regressions and plots.

References supporting supplementary methods

1. Miles A, pyup.io bot, Murillo R, Ralph P, Harding N, Pisupati R, et al. scikit-allel. v1.3.3 ed. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.47593682021>.
2. The Anopheles gambiae 1000 Genomes Consortium. Genetic diversity of the African malaria vector *Anopheles gambiae*. *Nature*. 2017;552(7683):96-100.
3. Isaacs AT, Mawejje HD, Tomlinson S, Rigden DJ, Donnelly MJ. Genome-wide transcriptional analyses in *Anopheles* mosquitoes reveal an unexpected association between salivary gland gene expression and insecticide resistance. *BMC genomics*. 2018;19(1):225.
4. Lucas ER, Miles A, Harding NJ, Clarkson CS, Lawniczak MKN, Kwiatkowski DP, et al. Whole-genome sequencing reveals high complexity of copy number variation at insecticide resistance loci in malaria mosquitoes. *Genome research*. 2019;29(8):1250-61.
5. Nagi S. anopheles-genomic-surveillance/selection-atlas: v0.0.1-beta. v0.0.1-beta ed. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10364083>: Zenodo; 2023.
6. Garud NR, Messer PW, Buzbas EO, Petrov DA. Recent selective sweeps in North American *Drosophila melanogaster* show signatures of soft sweeps. *PLoS genetics*. 2015;11(2):e1005004.
7. Nagi SC. AnoExpress. v0.2.0 ed. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7965646>: Zenodo; 2023.
8. Heinicke S, Livstone MS, Lu C, Oughtred R, Kang F, Angiuoli SV, et al. The Princeton Protein Orthology Database (P-POD): a comparative genomics analysis tool for biologists. *PLoS one*. 2007;2(8):e766.
9. Capra JA, Williams AG, Pollard KS. ProteinHistorian: tools for the comparative analysis of eukaryote protein origin. *PLoS computational biology*. 2012;8(6):e1002567.
10. Fontanillas P, Landry CR, Wittkopp PJ, Russ C, Gruber JD, Nusbaum C, et al. Key considerations for measuring allelic expression on a genomic scale using high-throughput sequencing. *Molecular ecology*. 2010;19 Suppl 1:212-27.
11. Turissini DA, Gamez S, White BJ. Genome-wide patterns of polymorphism in an inbred line of the African malaria mosquito *Anopheles gambiae*. *Genome biology and evolution*. 2014;6(11):3094-104.
12. Frochoux MV, Bou Sleiman M, Gardeux V, Dainese R, Hollis B, Litovchenko M, et al. cis-regulatory variation modulates susceptibility to enteric infection in the *Drosophila* genetic reference panel. *Genome biology*. 2020;21(1):6.
13. Floc'hlay S, Wong E, Zhao B, Viales RR, Thomas-Chollier M, Thieffry D, et al. Cis-acting variation is common across regulatory layers but is often buffered during embryonic development. *Genome research*. 2020.

14. Brooks ME, Kristensen K, van Benthem KJ, Magnusson A, Berg CW, Nielsen A, et al. glmmTMB Balances Speed and Flexibility Among Packages for Zero-inflated Generalized Linear Mixed Modeling. *The R Journal*. 2017;9(2):378-400.
15. R Core Team. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing <https://www.R-project.org/>; 2018.
16. Mendelevich A, Vinogradova S, Gupta S, Mironov AA, Sunyaev SR, Gimelbrant AA. Replicate sequencing libraries are important for quantification of allelic imbalance. *Nature communications*. 2021;12(1):3370.
17. Conway JR, Lex A, Gehlenborg N. UpSetR: an R package for the visualization of intersecting sets and their properties. *Bioinformatics*. 2017;33(18):2938-40.
18. Wickham H. ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis. Springer-Verlag New York; 2016.